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Some New Classes of Statistical Convergent Fuzzy Real-valued Triple Sequences

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Abstract: In this article, some new classes of statistical convergence of sequences of fuzzy real numbers have multiplicity greater than two is introduced. Certain Theorems regarding uniqueness of limit, algebraic characterization of statistical limit for triple sequences of fuzzy numbers are obtained. The decomposition theorem is proved. The inclusion relations are derived. The fuzzy real-valued Cesáro summable triple sequence space is also introduced. A relation between strongly p-Cesáro summability and bounded statistically convergent triple sequences has been established.

Key words and phrases: Density, triple sequence, statistical convergence, statistically Cauchy, fuzzy real-valued triple sequences, Cesáro summable, strong Cesáro summability.

1. Introduction

Fuzzy set theory, compared to other mathematical theories, is perhaps the most easily adaptable theory to practice. The concepts of fuzzy sets and fuzzy set operations were first introduced by Zadeh [35] in 1965 and subsequently several authors have discussed various aspects of the theory and applications of fuzzy sets. In fact the fuzzy set theory has become an area of active area of research in science and engineering for the last 46 years. Fuzzy set theory is a powerful hand set for modelling uncertainty and vagueness in various problems arising in the field of science and engineering. It extends the scope and results of classical mathematical analysis by applying fuzzy logic to conventional mathematical objects, such as functions, sequences and series etc.

As a generalization of ordinary convergence for sequences of real numbers, the notion of statistical convergence was first introduced by Fast [9]. After then it was studied by many researchers like Salat [24], Fridy [10], Connor [3], Maddox [15], Fridy and Orhan [11], Nuray [20], Subrahmanyam [28], Kwon [14], Savas [25], Demirci [4], Tripathy [29], Savas and Mursaleen [27]. Different classes of statistically convergent sequences were introduced and investigated by Tripathy and Sen [34], Tripathy [29], Tripathy and Dutta [31], Tripathy and Sarma [33] etc. Móricz [16] extended statistical convergence from single to multiple real sequences. Nuray and Savas [21] first defined the concepts of statistical convergence and statistically Cauchy for sequences of fuzzy numbers. Some more works on statistical convergence are found in Altin [2], Esi and Ozdemir [8], Gokhan *et al.* [12], Tripathy and Baruah [29] etc.

Agnew [1] studied the summability theory of multiple sequences and obtained certain theorems which have already been proved for double sequences by the author himself. The different types of notions of triple sequences was introduced and investigated at the initial stage by Sahiner *et al.* [22], Sahiner and Tripathy [23]. Recently Savas and Esi [26] have introduced statistical convergence of triple sequences on probabilistic normed space. Later on, Esi [7] have introduced statistical convergence of triple sequences in topological groups. Some more recent works on statistical triple sequences are found on Kumar *et al.* [13], Esi [6], Dutta *et al.* [5] etc.

A fuzzy real number on R is a mapping $X : R \rightarrow L(=[0,1])$ associating each real number $t \in R$ with

its grade of membership $X(t)$. Every real number r can be expressed as a fuzzy real number \bar{r} as follows:

$$\bar{r}(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } t = r \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The α -level set of a fuzzy real number X , $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, denoted by $[X]^\alpha$ is defined as

$$[X]^\alpha = \{t \in R : X(t) \geq \alpha\}.$$

A fuzzy real number X is called convex if $X(t) \geq X(s) \wedge X(r) = \min(X(s), X(r))$, where $s < t < r$. If there exists $t_0 \in R$ such that $X(t_0) = 1$, then the fuzzy real number X is called normal. A fuzzy real number X is said to be upper semi-continuous if for each $\varepsilon > 0, \setminus X^{-1}[0, a + \varepsilon)$, for all $a \in L$ is open in the usual topology of R . The set of all upper semi continuous, normal, convex fuzzy number is denoted by $R(L)$. The additive identity and multiplicative identity in $R(L)$ are denoted by $\bar{0}$ and $\bar{1}$ respectively.

Let D be the set of all closed bounded intervals $X = [X^L, X^R]$ on the real line R . Then

$$X \leq Y \text{ if and only if } X^L \leq Y^L \text{ and } X^R \leq Y^R. \text{ Also let } d(X, Y) = \max(|X^L - Y^L|, |Y^L - Y^R|).$$

Then (D, d) is a complete metric space.

Let $\bar{d} : R(L) \times R(L) \rightarrow R$ be defined by $\bar{d}(X, Y) = \sup_{0 \leq \alpha \leq 1} d([X]^\alpha, [Y]^\alpha)$, for $X, Y \in R(L)$.

Then \bar{d} defines a metric on $R(L)$.

Throughout the paper, \bar{d} denote a metric.

2. Preliminaries and background

Throughout the paper C, C_0, ℓ_∞ denote the spaces of convergent, null and bounded sequences respectively.

A triple sequence can be defined as a function $x : N \times N \times N \rightarrow R(C)$, where N, R and C denote the sets of natural numbers, real numbers and complex numbers respectively.

A fuzzy real-valued triple sequence $X = \langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ is a triple infinite array of fuzzy real numbers X_{nkl} for all $n, k, l \in N$ and is denoted by $\langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ where $X_{nkl} \in R(L)$.

The notion of statistical convergence for triple sequences depends on the density of the subsets of $N \times N \times N$. The notion of the asymptotic density for subsets of $N \times N \times N$ as follows:

A subset E of $N \times N \times N$ is said to have density or asymptotic density $\rho(E)$, if

$$\rho(E) = \lim_{p, q, r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{n=1}^p \sum_{k=1}^q \sum_{l=1}^r \chi_E(n, k, l)}{pqr} \text{ exists, where } \chi_E \text{ is the characteristic function of } E.$$

Obviously $\rho(E^c) = \rho(N \times N \times N - E) = 1 - \rho(E)$.

A fuzzy real-valued triple sequence $X = \langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ is said to be statistically convergent in Pringsheim's sense to the fuzzy real number X_0 , if for all $\varepsilon > 0$, the set $\rho\{(n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : \bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0) \geq \varepsilon\} = 0$.

We write $stat_3 - \lim_{n, k, l \rightarrow \infty} X_{nkl} = X_0$.

A fuzzy real-valued triple sequence $X = \langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ is said to be statistically null if it is statistically convergent to zero.

A fuzzy real-valued triple sequence $X = \langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ is said to be statistically bounded if there exists a real number μ such that $\rho\{(n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : \bar{d}(X_{nkl}, \bar{0}) > \mu\} = 0$.

A fuzzy real-valued triple sequence $X = \langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ is said to be statistically Cauchy if for every $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists $p = p(\varepsilon)$, $q = q(\varepsilon)$ and $r = r(\varepsilon) \in N$ such that $\rho(\{(n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : \bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_{pqr}) \geq \varepsilon\}) = 0$.

A fuzzy real-valued triple sequence $X = \langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ is said to be statistically regularly convergent if it is convergent in Pringsheim's sense and in addition the following statistical limits holds:

$$stat_3 - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} X_{nkl} = L_{kl} (k, l \in N);$$

$$stat_3 - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} X_{nkl} = L_{nl} (n, l \in N);$$

and

$$stat_3 - \lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} X_{nkl} = L_{nk} (n, k \in N);$$

Different classes of fuzzy sequencespaces were introduced and investigated by many authors. Recent works on fuzzy triple sequences are found in Nath and Roy ([17], [18], [19]).

A fuzzy real-valued triple sequence $\langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ is said to be Cesàro summable to a fuzzy real number X_0 , if

$$\lim_{u, v, w \rightarrow \infty} \bar{d} \left(\frac{1}{uvw} \left(\sum_{n=1}^u \sum_{l=1}^v \sum_{k=1}^w X_{nkl} \right), X_0 \right) = 0.$$

A fuzzy real-valued triple sequence $\langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ is said to be strongly p -Cesàro summable to a fuzzy real

$$\text{number } X_0, \text{ if } \lim_{u, v, w \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{uvw} \sum_{n=1}^u \sum_{l=1}^v \sum_{k=1}^w (\bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0))^p = 0.$$

We denote the space of all strongly p -Cesàro summable triple sequences of fuzzy real numbers by $(w^F)_3^P$.

Let $\langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ and $\langle Y_{nkl} \rangle$ be two triple sequences of fuzzy real numbers, then $X_{nkl} = Y_{nkl}$ for almost all n, l and k (in short *a.a.* n, k and l) if $\rho(\{(n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : X_{nkl} \neq Y_{nkl}\}) = 0$.

Remark 2.1. If a sequence space E^F is solid, then it is monotone.

Throughout the article $(w^F)_3, (\ell_\infty^F)_3, (\bar{c}^F)_3^R, (\bar{c}_0^F)_3^R, (\bar{c}^F)_3^P, (\bar{c}_0^F)_3^P$ denote the spaces of all, bounded, statistically regularly convergent, statistically regularly null, statistically convergent in Pringsheim's sense and statistically null in Pringsheim's sense triple sequence spaces of fuzzy real numbers respectively.

Also the following sequence spaces are introduced:

$$(\bar{c}^F)_3^{RB} = (\bar{c}^F)_3^R \cap (\ell_\infty^F)_3;$$

$$(\bar{c}_0^F)_3^{RB} = (\bar{c}_0^F)_3^R \cap (\ell_\infty^F)_3;$$

$$(\bar{c}^F)_3^{PB} = (\bar{c}^F)_3^P \cap (\ell_\infty^F)_3;$$

$$(\bar{c}_0^F)_3^{PB} = (\bar{c}_0^F)_3^P \cap (\ell_\infty^F)_3.$$

From the above definitions, it follows that $(c)_3^P \subset (\bar{c}^F)_3^P, (c_0)_3^P \subset (\bar{c}_0^F)_3^P, (c)_3^{PB} \subset (\bar{c}^F)_3^{PB}$ and $(c_0)_3^{PB} \subset (\bar{c}_0^F)_3^{PB}$ and the inclusions are proper.

3. Main Results:

Theorem 3.1. Every convergent triple sequence of fuzzy real number is statistically convergent, but the converse is not necessarily true.

Proof. Since the asymptotic density of finite subsets of $N \times N \times N$ is zero, it follows that every convergent triple sequence of fuzzy real number is statistically convergent.

But the converse is not necessarily true as seen from the following example.

Example 3.1. For every $t \in R$, consider a sequence $X = \langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ of fuzzy numbers defined as follows:

For $n = p^2, k = q^2, l = r^2, p, q, r \in N$

$$X_{nkl}(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } t \in (-\infty, nkl-1) \cup (nkl+1, \infty) \\ t - (nkl-1), & \text{if } t \in [nkl-1, nkl] \\ -t + (nkl+1), & \text{if } t \in [nkl, nkl+1] \end{cases}$$

Otherwise $X_{nkl} = X_0$, where X_0 is given by

$$X_0(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } t \in (-\infty, 0) \cup (2, \infty) \\ t, & \text{if } t \in [0, 1] \\ -t + 2, & \text{if } t \in [1, 2] \end{cases}$$

Now, for $0 < \varepsilon < 1$, we have

$$\{(n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : \bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0) \geq \varepsilon\} \subset \{(n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : n = p^2, k = q^2, l = r^2, p, q, r \in N\}$$

Since, the later set has triple density zero, it follows that

$$\rho(\{(n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : d(X_{nkl}, X_0) \geq \varepsilon\}) = 0.$$

$\therefore \text{stat}_3 - \lim_{n, k, l \rightarrow \infty} X_{nkl} = X_0$. But, the sequence $X = \langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ is not ordinarily convergent to X_0 . ■

With the usual technique, the following theorem can be proved easily.

Theorem 3.2. If a triple sequence $\langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ of fuzzy real numbers is statistically convergent to L , then L is determined uniquely.

We now give algebraic characterization of statistical limit for triple sequences of fuzzy real numbers in the following theorem.

Theorem 3.3. Let $\langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ and $\langle Y_{nkl} \rangle$ be two triple sequences of fuzzy real numbers. Then

(i) If $\langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ is statistically convergent to X_0 and $c \in \mathbb{R}$, then $\langle cX_{nkl} \rangle$ is statistically convergent to cX_0 .

(ii) If $\langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ and $\langle Y_{nkl} \rangle$ are statistically convergent to fuzzy numbers X_0 and Y_0 respectively, then $\langle X_{nkl} + Y_{nkl} \rangle$ is statistically convergent to $X_0 + Y_0$.

Proof. (i) Let $stat_3 - \lim_{n,k,l \rightarrow \infty} X_{nkl} = X_0$.

Then for any $\varepsilon > 0$,

$$\therefore \rho(\{(n,k,l) \in N \times N \times N : \bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0) \geq \varepsilon\}) = 0.$$

Let $\alpha \in [0,1]$. Let X_{nkl}^α and X_0^α be α -level sets of X_{nkl} and X_0 respectively.

Since $d(cX_{nkl}^\alpha, cX_0^\alpha) = |c|d(X_{nkl}^\alpha, X_0^\alpha)$, for $c \in \mathbb{R}$.

$$\Rightarrow \sup_{\alpha} d(cX_{nkl}^\alpha, cX_0^\alpha) = |c| \sup_{\alpha} d(X_{nkl}^\alpha, X_0^\alpha)$$

$$\Rightarrow \bar{d}(cX_{nkl}, cX_0) = |c| \bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0)$$

This gives for $\varepsilon > 0$,

$$\frac{1}{pqr} \left| \{(n,k,l) \in N \times N \times N : n \leq p; k \leq q, l \leq r : \bar{d}(cX_{nkl}, cX_0) \geq \varepsilon\} \right|$$

$$\leq \frac{1}{pqr} \left| \{(n,k,l) \in N \times N \times N : n \leq p; k \leq q, l \leq r : \bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0) \geq \frac{\varepsilon}{|c|}\} \right|$$

$$\lim_{p,q,r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{pqr} \left| \{(n,k,l) \in N \times N \times N : n \leq p; k \leq q, l \leq r : \bar{d}(cX_{nkl}, cX_0) \geq \varepsilon\} \right| = 0,$$

$$\therefore \rho(\{(n,k,l) \in N \times N \times N : \bar{d}(cX_{nkl}, cX_0) \geq \varepsilon\}) = 0.$$

Hence $stat_3 - \lim_{n,k,l \rightarrow \infty} cX_{nkl} = cX_0$.

(ii) Let $stat_3 - \lim_{n,k,l \rightarrow \infty} cX_{nkl} = cX_0$ and $stat_3 - \lim_{n,k,l \rightarrow \infty} cY_{nkl} = cY_0$.

$$\therefore \rho(\{(n,k,l) \in N \times N \times N : \bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0) \geq \varepsilon\}) = 0 \text{ and } \rho(\{(n,k,l) \in N \times N \times N : \bar{d}(Y_{nkl}, Y_0) \geq \varepsilon\}) = 0.$$

Let $\alpha \in [0,1]$. Let $X_{nkl}^\alpha, Y_{nkl}^\alpha, X_0^\alpha$ and Y_0^α be the α -level sets of X_{nkl}, Y_{nkl}, X_0 and Y_0 respectively.

$$\text{Now } d(X_{nkl}^\alpha + Y_{nkl}^\alpha, X_0^\alpha + Y_0^\alpha) \leq d(X_{nkl}^\alpha, X_0^\alpha) + d(Y_{nkl}^\alpha, Y_0^\alpha)$$

$$\Rightarrow \sup_{\alpha} d(X_{nkl}^\alpha + Y_{nkl}^\alpha, X_0^\alpha + Y_0^\alpha) \leq \sup_{\alpha} d(X_{nkl}^\alpha, X_0^\alpha) + d(Y_{nkl}^\alpha, Y_0^\alpha)$$

$$\Rightarrow \bar{d}(X_{nkl}^\alpha + Y_{nkl}^\alpha, X_0^\alpha + Y_0^\alpha) \leq \bar{d}(X_{nkl}^\alpha, X_0^\alpha) + \bar{d}(Y_{nkl}^\alpha, Y_0^\alpha)$$

For a given $\varepsilon > 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{pqr} \left| \left\{ (n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : n \leq p; k \leq q, l \leq r : \bar{d}(X_{nkl} + Y_{nkl}, X_0 + Y_0) \geq \varepsilon \right\} \right| \\ & \leq \frac{1}{pqr} \left| \left\{ (n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : n \leq p; k \leq q, l \leq r : \bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0) + \bar{d}(Y_{nkl}, Y_0) \geq \varepsilon \right\} \right| \\ & \leq \frac{1}{pqr} \left| \left\{ n, k, l \in N \times N \times N : n \leq p; k \leq q, l \leq r : \bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0) \geq \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \right\} \right| + \\ & \frac{1}{pqr} \left| \left\{ n, k, l \in N \times N \times N : n \leq p; k \leq q, l \leq r : \bar{d}(Y_{nkl}, Y_0) \geq \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \right\} \right|. \\ & \lim_{p, q, r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{pqr} \left| \left\{ (n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : n \leq p; k \leq q, l \leq r : \bar{d}(X_{nkl} + Y_{nkl}, X_0 + Y_0) \geq \varepsilon \right\} \right| = 0, \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore \rho\{(n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : \bar{d}(X_{nkl} + Y_{nkl}, X_0 + Y_0) \geq \varepsilon\} = 0.$$

Hence $stat_3 - \lim_{n, k, l \rightarrow \infty} X_{nkl} + X_{nkl} = X_0 + Y_0$. ■

The following result, known as the **decomposition theorem** for statistically convergent fuzzy real-valued triple sequence space.

Theorem 3.4. *The following statements are equivalent:*

- (i) *The triple sequence $\langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ of fuzzy real numbers is statistically convergent to X_0 .*
- (ii) *There exists a triple sequence $\langle Y_{nkl} \rangle \in (\bar{C}^F)_3^P$ such that $X_{nkl} = Y_{nkl}$ for a.a. n, k and l .*
- (iii) *There exists a subset $M = \{n_p, k_q, l_r\} \in N \times N \times N : p, q, r \in N\}$ of $N \times N \times N$ such that $\rho(M) = 1$ and $\langle X_{n_p k_q l_r} \rangle \in (\bar{C}^F)_3^P$.*
- (iv) *There exists two triple sequences $\langle A_{nkl} \rangle$ and $\langle B_{nkl} \rangle$ of fuzzy real numbers such that $X_{nkl} = A_{nkl} + B_{nkl}$ for all $n, k, l \in N$, where $\langle A_{nkl} \rangle$ converges to X_0 and $\langle B_{nkl} \rangle \in (\bar{C}_0^F)_3^P$.*

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii). Let $stat_3 - \lim_{n, k, l \rightarrow \infty} X_{nkl} = X_0$. Then for every $\varepsilon > 0$,

$$\rho\{(n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : \bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0) \geq \varepsilon\} = 0.$$

Now selecting the increasing sequences (T_j) , (U_j) and (V_j) of natural numbers such that if

$$p > T_j, q > U_j \text{ and } r > V_j, \text{ then } \frac{1}{pqr} \left| \left\{ (n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : n \leq p; k \leq q; l \leq r : \bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0) \geq \frac{1}{j} \right\} \right| < \frac{1}{j}, \text{ where } |E|$$

denote the cardinality of the set E .

Consider the sequence $\langle Y_{nkl} \rangle$ defined as follows:

$$Y_{nkl} = X_{nkl}, \text{ if } n \leq T_1 \text{ or } k \leq U_1 \text{ or } l \leq V_1.$$

Next for all (n, k, l) with $T_j < n \leq T_{j+1}$ or $U_j < k \leq U_{j+1}$, or $V_j < l \leq V_{j+1}$,

let $Y_{nkl} = X_{nkl}$, if $\bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0) < \frac{1}{j}$, otherwise, $Y_{nkl} = X_0$.

Let $\varepsilon > 0$ be given and choosing j such that $\varepsilon < \frac{1}{j}$.

For $n > T_j, k > U_j$ and $l > V_j$, we find that $\bar{d}(Y_{nkl}, X_0) < \varepsilon$.

The fact that $Y_{nkl} = X_{nkl}$, for a.a. n, k and l . follows from the following inclusion:

Let $T_j < n \leq T_{j+1}, U_j < k \leq U_{j+1}$ and $V_j < l \leq V_{j+1}$, then

$$\begin{aligned} & \{(n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : n \leq p; k \leq q, l \leq r \text{ and } X_{nkl} \neq Y_{nkl}\} \\ & \subseteq \{(n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : n \leq p; k \leq q, l \leq r \text{ and } \bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0) \geq \frac{1}{j}\} \\ & \Rightarrow \frac{1}{pqr} |\{(n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : n \leq p; k \leq q, l \leq r \text{ and } X_{nkl} \neq Y_{nkl}\}| \\ & \leq \frac{1}{pqr} \left| \left\{ (n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : n \leq p; k \leq q, l \leq r \text{ and } \bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0) \geq \frac{1}{j} \right\} \right| < \frac{1}{j}, \\ & \Rightarrow \lim_{p, q, r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{pqr} |\{(n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : n \leq p; k \leq q, l \leq r \text{ and } X_{nkl} \neq Y_{nkl}\}| = 0. \end{aligned}$$

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii) Let there exists a sequence $\langle X_{nkl} \rangle \in (\bar{C}^F)_3^P$ such that $X_{nkl} = Y_{nkl}$ for a.a. n, k and l .

Let $M = \{(n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : X_{nkl} = Y_{nkl}\}$, then $\rho(M) = 1$.

Now enumerate M as $M = \{(n_p, k_q, l_r) \in N \times N \times N : p, q, r \in N\}$ on neglecting the rows and columns those contain finite number of elements.

Clearly $\rho(M) = 1$ and $\bar{d}(X_{n_p k_q l_r}, X_0) = \bar{d}(Y_{n_p k_q l_r}, X_0) \rightarrow 0$ as $p, q, r \rightarrow \infty$.

$$\Rightarrow \langle X_{n_p k_q l_r} \rangle \in (\bar{C}^F)_3^P.$$

(iii) \Rightarrow (iv). Let $\langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ be a triple sequence and there exists $M = \{(n_p, k_q, l_r) \in N \times N \times N : p, q, r \in N\}$ be such that $\rho(M) = 1$ and $\lim_{p, q, r \rightarrow \infty} X_{n_p k_q l_r} = X_0$.

Now, two triple sequences $\langle A_{nkl} \rangle$ and $\langle B_{nkl} \rangle$ of fuzzy real numbers are constructed as follows:

$$A_{nkl} \begin{cases} X_{nkl}, & \text{if } (n, k, l) \in N, \\ X_0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$B_{nkl} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } (n, k, l) \in N, \\ X_{nkl} - X_0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

From the above construction, it is clear that $\langle A_{nkl} \rangle$ converges to X_0 and $\langle B_{nkl} \rangle \in (\bar{C}_0^F)_3^P$ and

$$X_{nkl} = A_{nkl} + B_{nkl} \text{ for all } n, k, l \in N,$$

(iv) \Rightarrow (i). Let there exists two triple sequences $\langle A_{nkl} \rangle$ and $\langle B_{nkl} \rangle$ of fuzzy real numbers such that

$$X_{nkl} = A_{nkl} + B_{nkl} \text{ for all } n, k, l \in N, \text{ where } \langle A_{nkl} \rangle \text{ converges to } X_0 \text{ and } \langle B_{nkl} \rangle \in (\bar{C}_0^F)_3^P.$$

For any $\varepsilon > 0$,

$$\text{Let } A = \left\{ (n, k, l) : \bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0) < \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \right\} \text{ and } B = \left\{ (n, k, l) : \bar{d}(X_{nkl}, \bar{0}) < \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \right\}.$$

Then clearly

$$\rho(A) = \rho(B) = 1. \text{ Let } E = A \cap B, \text{ then } \rho(E) = 1 \text{ and}$$

$$\therefore \rho(\{(n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : \bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0) < \varepsilon\}) \geq \rho(E) = 1.$$

$$\Rightarrow \rho(\{(n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : \bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0) \geq \varepsilon\}) = 0.$$

$$\therefore \text{stat}_3 - \lim_{n, k, l \rightarrow \infty} X_{nkl} = X_0. \blacksquare$$

Theorem 3.5. A triple sequence $\langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ of fuzzy real numbers is statistically convergent, if and only if $\langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ is a statistical Cauchy sequence.

Proof. Let $\text{stat}_3 - \lim_{n, k, l \rightarrow \infty} X_{nkl} = X_0$.

Then for each $\varepsilon \geq 0$,

$$\rho(\{(n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : \bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0) \geq \varepsilon\}) = 0.$$

Choose numbers p, q and r such that $\bar{d}(X_{pqr}, X_0) \geq \varepsilon$.

Now let

$$A = \{(n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N, n \leq u, k \leq v, l \leq w : \bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_{pqr}) \geq \varepsilon\};$$

$$B = \{(n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N, n \leq u, k \leq v, l \leq w : \bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0) \geq \varepsilon\};$$

$$C = \{(p, q, r) \in N \times N \times N : \bar{d}(X_{pqr}, X_0) \geq \varepsilon\}.$$

Then $A \subseteq B \cup C$ and therefore $\rho(A) \leq \rho(B) + \rho(C) = 0$. Hence $\langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ is statistically Cauchy.

Conversely, let $\langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ be statistically Cauchy. Then for a given $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists $n_0(\varepsilon), k_0(\varepsilon)$ and

$$l_0(\varepsilon) \in N \text{ such that } \rho(\{(n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : \bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_{pqr}) \geq \varepsilon\}) = 0.$$

i.e. $\bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_{n_0 k_0 l_0}) < \varepsilon$, for a.a. n, k and l . Now choose n_1, k_1, l_1 such that $X_{nkl} \in U_1(X_{n_1 k_1 l_1}, 1)$, for a.a.

n, k and l . Next choose n_2, k_2, l_2 such that $X_{nkl} \in U_2(X_{n_2 k_2 l_2}, 2^{-1})$, for a.a. n, k and l .

Let $U^1 = U_1 \cap U_2$. Clearly U^1 contains X_{nkl} for a.a. for a.a. n, k and l and the diameter of U^1 is less than or equal to 1. Similarly one can get a closed ball $U_3(X_{n_3k_3l_3}, 2^{-2})$, which contains X_{nkl} for a.a. n, k and l . The diameter of U^2 is less than or equal to 2^{-1} . Proceeding in this way, a nest of closed balls $\{U^j\}$, is obtained such that $X_{nkl} \in U^j$, for a.a. n, k and l and the diameter of U^j is less than or equal to 2^{1-j} . Then by the theorem of nested property of closed fuzzy sets, $\bigcap_{j=1}^{\infty} U^j$ contains exactly one element.

Let $\bigcap_{j=1}^{\infty} U^j = \{X_0\}$. Let $\varepsilon > 0$ be given and let t be a constant satisfying $\varepsilon > 2^{1-t}$. Then $X_{nkl} \in U^t$, for a.a. n, k and l , which gives $\bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0) \leq 2^{1-t} < \varepsilon$, for a.a. n, k and l .

This implies that $stat_3 - \lim_{n,k,l \rightarrow \infty} X_{nkl} = X_0$. ■

Theorem 3.6. (i) Let $p \in (0, \infty)$. If a triple sequence $\langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ of fuzzy real number is strongly p -Cesàro summable to a fuzzy number X_0 , then it is also statistically convergent to X_0 .

(ii) Let $p \in (0, \infty)$. If a bounded triple sequence $\langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ of fuzzy real number is statistically convergent to X_0 , then it is strongly p -Cesàro summable to X_0 .

Proof. (i) Let $\langle X_{nkl} \rangle \in (W^F)_3^p$ be such that $\langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ is strongly p -Cesàro summable to a fuzzy number X_0 .

$$\text{Then } \lim_{u,v,w \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{uvw} \sum_{n=1}^u \sum_{l=1}^v \sum_{k=1}^w (\bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0))^p = 0.$$

Now for any $\varepsilon > 0$,

$$\frac{1}{uvw} \sum_{n=1}^u \sum_{l=1}^v \sum_{k=1}^w (\bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0))^p \geq \frac{1}{uvw} |\{(n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : n \leq u; k \leq v, l \leq w : (\bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0))^p \geq \varepsilon\}|.$$

Now taking limits as $u, v, w \rightarrow \infty$,

$$stat_3 - \lim_{n,k,l \rightarrow \infty} X_{nkl} = X_0.$$

Again for a bounded triple sequence $\langle X_{nkl} \rangle$, let $stat_3 - \lim_{n,k,l \rightarrow \infty} X_{nkl} = X_0$.

$$\text{Let } K = \bar{d}(X_{nkl}, \bar{0}) + \bar{d}(X_0, \bar{0}).$$

Let $\varepsilon > 0$ be given, then there exist u_0, v_0, w_0 such that

$$\frac{1}{uvw} \left| \left\{ (n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : n \leq u; k \leq v, l \leq w; \bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0) \geq \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{2}\right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \right\} \right| < \frac{\varepsilon}{2K^p}, \text{ for all } u > u_0, v > v_0$$

and $w > w_0$.

$$\text{Let } L_{uvw} = \left\{ (n, k, l) \in N \times N \times N : n \leq u; k \leq v; l \leq w; (\bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0))^p \geq \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \right\}.$$

Now for all $u > u_0, v > v_0$ and $w > w_0$,

$$\frac{1}{uvw} \sum_{n=1}^u \sum_{k=1}^v \sum_{l=1}^w (\bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0))^p = \frac{1}{uvw} \left\{ \sum_{(n,k,l) \in L_{uvw}} \sum (\bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0))^p \right\} + \frac{1}{uvw} \left\{ \sum_{(n,k,l) \notin L_{uvw}} \sum (\bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0))^p \right\}$$

$$< \frac{1}{uvw} \left\{ uvw \frac{\varepsilon}{2K^p} \cdot K^p + uvw \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \right\} < \varepsilon.$$

$$\therefore \lim_{u,v,w \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{uvw} \sum_{n=1}^u \sum_{k=1}^v \sum_{l=1}^w (\bar{d}(X_{nkl}, X_0))^p = 0.$$

Hence $\langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ is strongly p -Cesàro summable to X_0 . ■

In view of the above theorem, the following results can be obtained.

Corollary 3.1. Let $0 < p < q < \infty$. Then $(w^F)_3^q \subset (w^F)_3^p$ and $(w^F)_3^p \cap (\ell^F)_3^\infty = (w^F)_3^q \cap (\ell^F)_3^\infty$.

Corollary 3.2. If a bounded triple sequence $\langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ of fuzzy real number is statistically convergent to X_0 , then it is Cesàro summable to X_0 .

Remark 3.1. If a bounded triple sequence $\langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ of fuzzy real number is Cesàro summable, then $\langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ may not be statistically convergent.

It follows from the following example.

Example 3.1. Let $X = \langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ be defined as $X_{nkl} = (-1)^n$, for all k, l . Then X is Cesàro summable but not statistically convergent.

Remark 3.2. If $X = \langle X_{nkl} \rangle$ is unbounded triple sequence of fuzzy real number, then X is statistically convergent but X is not necessarily strongly p -Cesàro summable.

The remark follows from the following example.

Example 3.2. Let $X = \langle X_{nkl} \rangle \in R(L)$ be defined as

For $n = i^2, i \in N$ and for all $k, l \in N$,

$$X_{nkl}(t) = \begin{cases} 1 + \frac{t}{\sqrt{n}}, & \text{for } -\sqrt{n} \leq t \leq 0 \\ 1 - \frac{t}{\sqrt{n}}, & \text{for } 0 \leq t \leq \sqrt{n} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

For $n \neq i^2, i \in N$ and for all $k, l \in N, X_{nkl}(t) = \bar{0}$.

The sequence X is unbounded and statistically convergent to $\bar{0}$.

$$\text{But for } p = 1, \lim_{u,v,w \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{uvw} \sum_{n=1}^u \sum_{k=1}^v \sum_{l=1}^w (\bar{d}(X_{nkl}, \bar{0}))^p = 1$$

Hence X is not strongly Cesáro summable to $\bar{0}$. ■

Conclusion:

Convergence theory is used as a basic tool in, measure spaces, sequences of random variables, information theory etc. We have introduced and studied some new classes of statistical convergence of sequences of fuzzy real numbers having multiplicity greater than two. Certain Theorems regarding uniqueness of limit, algebraic characterization of statistical limit for triple sequences of fuzzy numbers are obtained. The decomposition theorem is proved. The inclusion relations are derived. The fuzzy real-valued Cesáro summable triple sequence space is also introduced. A relation between strongly p -Cesáro summability and bounded statistically convergent triple sequences is established.

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